

STRESS ANALYSIS OF FIBRE REINFORCED COMPOSITE SYSTEMS BY THERMOELASTIC EMISSION

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ABSTRACT

A one-dimensional and a three-dimensional numerical model, based on the non-adiabatic theory, is described and experimentally validated for different composite systems. It is seen that the spate-data on composite systems is frequency dependent and consequently that the interpretation of the data is not straight-forward unless the loading frequency is extremely high.

Keywords: Spate, Thermoelasticity, stress analysis.

1. INTRODUCTION

The thermoelastic stress analysis is based on the principle, that the temperature of a body changes when the stress state changes. As long as adiabatic conditions are maintained and the body is loaded within the elastic range, this temperature change is proportional to the change in the sum of the principal stresses. Although the discovery of this effect was first made by W. Weber [1] in 1830 and theoretically treated by Lord Kelvin [2] in 1853 it was, at that time, technologically impossible to measure these small temperature changes and consequently use the thermoelastic effect to indicate stresses in a structure under load.

Recent development in infra-red technology and signal processing were necessary before a highly sensitive equipment (SPATE - Stress Pattern Analysis by the measurement of Thermal Emission) became available for this purpose. Though relatively young, the use of SPATE as a remote infra-red sensing technique to produce full-field stress maps, became increasingly widespread, particularly for metallic structures. A selected number of papers confirmed the validity of the theoretical basis of the technique and demonstrated its scope and potential. Especially P. Stanley [3] used SPATE to study the stress distribution in beams, "Brazilian" discs, rectangular plates and circular rings.

The agreement between the experimental and numerical results was very good. H. Wölfel [4] showed an excellent agreement between stress results obtained by thermoelastic stress analysis and Finite Elements. However, on composite structures the thermoelastic stress analysis has thus far been limited primarily to simple studies and to qualitative NDT-type applications (e.g. [5,6]). The reason for this is largely due to a general lack of a thorough understanding of the thermoelastic behaviour of composite materials. The thermal analysis [7,8] of a single fiber, simulated as an infinitely long circular cylinder, and a single ply, simulated as an infinite plate, subjected to a sudden change in temperature at both its surfaces showed that the fiber and its surrounding matrix experience the same temperature fluctuations but that a complete homogenisation of the temperature between the different layers of a laminate may not occur.

2. A THREE DIMENSIONAL MODEL FOR COMPOSITE SYSTEMS

2.1. Theory.

For a more accurate representation of the problem we will include in the analysis the process of heat transfer between the different layers.

Since each ply can be treated as a homogeneous orthotropic plate, it may be shown from the principles of continuum mechanics and the thermoelasticity of irreversible processes that, for quasi-static conditions and small temperature changes :

$$\sum_{i=1}^3 \frac{\partial q_i}{\partial x_i} = -\rho c_{\sigma} \frac{\partial T}{\partial t} - T_0 (\alpha_{11} \dot{\sigma}_{11} + \alpha_{22} \dot{\sigma}_{22}) \quad (1)$$

where q_i is the heat flux passing through the point under consideration, ρ is the density, c_{σ} is the specific heat under constant stress, T_0 is the absolute temperature, α_{11} , α_{22} are the coefficients of thermal expansion and σ_{11} , σ_{22} are the stress components in the respective inplane orthotropic directions.

The applications of Fourier's law of heat conduction gives

$$\sum_{i=1}^3 \frac{\partial q_i}{\partial x_i} = -K_i \frac{\partial^2 T}{\partial x_i^2} \quad (2)$$

where x_i are the orthotropic directions and K_i the corresponding heat conduction coefficients.

Defining the non-dimensional temperature θ as:
$$\theta = \frac{T - T_0}{T_0} \quad (3)$$

and substituting equation (2) into equation (1) yields the classical heat-conduction equation:

$$\rho c_{\sigma} \frac{\partial \theta}{\partial t} - K_i \frac{\partial^2 \theta}{\partial x_i^2} = S \quad (4)$$

where : $S = - [\alpha_{11} \dot{\sigma}_{11} + \alpha_{22} \dot{\sigma}_{22}]$

Any material that has orthotropic symmetry will possess only three independent thermal conductivities, K_{11} , K_{22} and K_{33} when the global x, y, z coordinate-axes are taken to be parallel to the principal axes of the material.

For a composite laminate composed of several layers of material oriented in different directions, it is more convenient to choose one fixed set of coordinate axes.

If one considers only rotations in the 1,2-plane, the thermal conductivity tensor becomes, with respect to the general x,y -coordinate system

$$\begin{Bmatrix} K_{xx} \\ K_{yy} \\ K_{xy} \end{Bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} \cos^2\theta & \sin^2\theta \\ \sin^2\theta & \cos^2\theta \\ \cos\theta \sin\theta & -\cos\theta \sin\theta \end{bmatrix} \begin{Bmatrix} K_{11} \\ K_{22} \end{Bmatrix} \quad (5)$$

and $K_{zz} = K_{33}$

The heat-conduction equation for this lamina can now be written as:

$$\rho c_{\sigma} \frac{\partial \theta}{\partial t} - K_{xx} \frac{\partial^2 \theta}{\partial x^2} - K_{yy} \frac{\partial^2 \theta}{\partial y^2} - K_{zz} \frac{\partial^2 \theta}{\partial z^2} - 2K_{xy} K_{xy} \frac{\partial^2 \theta}{\partial x \partial y} = S \quad (6)$$

Since the heat-conduction coefficient in the through-thickness direction is independent of the layer-orientation, equation (6), though derived for a single lamina, may in the case where all plies are of the same material, be applied for the whole laminate. However, since the stresses can vary from ply to ply, the heat input S in equation (6) will in general be a discontinuous function through the thickness of the laminate.

To solve equation (6) an explicit finite-difference method is used. The spatial and time derivatives in equation (6) are replaced by the finite difference approximations based upon Taylor expansions.

The boundary conditions used for $t \geq 0$ are:

- (1) an adiabatic midplane due to the symmetric stacking sequence of the composite laminate
- (2) adiabatic surfaces along the short edges, that is, along the clamped edge in the y - z plane where the test specimen is fixed in the grips of the testing machine
- (3) convective surfaces along the top surface and long edges, that is, along the free edge in the x - z plane.

2.2. NUMERICAL RESULTS.

Based upon the previously discussed three-dimensional heat-conduction model, a computer code, written in the language C, was developed on the CRAY Y-MP, in order to calculate the temperature distribution on the surface of a laminate.

Typically, an area of 10 mm by 10 mm was discretised by 41 nodes in the x-direction and by 41 nodes in the y-direction. In the thickness direction each lamina was subdivided by 5 sublayers. This means that for each time step the temperature in about 35.300 points need to be updated.

In order to achieve steady-state conditions, 10 periods were calculated for each frequency. To fulfil the requirement for numerical stability the time increment had to be smaller than $8 \cdot 10^{-4}$ seconds.

The calculation time on the CRAY Y-MP was only 20 CPU-seconds.

The material properties used in the calculations are given in table 1.

	Averaged values	Std Dev.
E_{11}	135.7 GPa	4.6 GPa
E_{22}	9.53 GPa	0.4 GPa
ν_{12}	0.32	0.012
G_{12}	4.74 GPa	0.5 GPa
c_{σ}	875 J/Kg °C	1 %
K_z	0.547 W/m°K	
α_{11}	$0.394 \cdot 10^{-6} / ^\circ\text{C}$	
α_{22}	$29.9 \cdot 10^{-6} / ^\circ\text{C}$	

Table 1. Mechanical properties of Ciba-Geigy Fibredux 914C-TS.

Unfortunately, as we did not measure the heat conduction coefficient in the inplane directions this data was taken from ref. [9] (i.e. $K_{11} = 4.3138 \text{ W/m}^\circ\text{C}$). For the heat conduction coefficient in the direction perpendicular to the fiber direction, we assumed the same value as the one in the thickness direction (i.e. $K_{22} = K_{zz} = 0.547 \text{ W/m}^\circ\text{C}$).

In the literature, the value of the coefficient of heat convection varies from $1 \text{ W/m}^2\text{C}$ [10] to $29 \text{ W/m}^2\text{C}$ [9]. In this simulation the maximum value of $29 \text{ W/m}^2\text{C}$ was used.

In order to check the influence of the convective boundary conditions and the uniformity of the surface temperature distribution a first set of simulations was run using a $[0^\circ, 90_2, 0^\circ]_S$ carbon epoxy specimen.

The surface temperature distribution for loading frequencies of 1,3 and 5 Hz. were calculated. Although at 1 Hz the disturbances close to the right and left edge are obvious the temperature variations are all below 1%. The distance from the edge which is disturbed by the convective heat loss is about the thickness of the laminate. When we load the same specimen at a frequency of 3 Hz

instead of 1 Hz the temperature variations are even lower and the disturbed distance reduces to a quarter of the thickness of the laminate. For a loading frequency of 5 Hz. temperature distribution is practically uniform except for areas very close to the edges, where still some slight variation is visible. Anyhow, as the width of the specimens used for the experimental measurements is 4 times larger than the width of the specimen used in this simulation we may conclude that the influence of the convective free edges will be completely negligible.

Beside the problem of the convective free edges, in real applications we will also have to deal with important stress gradients within the bulk material. To evaluate this effect the temperature distribution due to a point heat source located in the centre of all the plies was calculated. The magnitude of the heat source "S" corresponds to a stress level of 1 N/mm².

The first specimen calculated was a [0°, 90°₂, 0°]_S carbon-epoxy of 10 mm by 10 mm subdivided in both directions by 40 elements.

The material data used in the calculation are the same as above.

It was found that for a loading frequency of 1 Hz the temperature field changed only in a relatively small area around the center. The diameter of the influenced zone was 4mm.

The result for a loading frequency of 10 Hz showed that the temperature distribution was nearly uniform except for a small area with a diameter of 1.3 mm. This area is nearly equal to the area covered by the specified heat source (about 1 mm). This means that points, at a distance larger than 1 mm away from each other, and having a different stress induced temperature variation will not influence each other.

3. A ONE DIMENSIONAL MODEL FOR COMPOSITE SYSTEMS

From the results of the three-dimensional heat-conduction model discussed in the previous chapter we may conclude that, as long as the stress gradients in the inplane directions are small compared to the the stress gradients in the thickness directions, all the points on the surface experience the same stress induced temperature fluctuation. Hence, if we assume that the process of heat transfer is dominated by diffusion in the through thickness direction, we may consider the development of a one-dimensional model. From this simplification certainly the computation time will benefit.

Defining the non-dimensional temperature as: $\theta = \frac{T - T_0}{T_0}$

and taking the heat conduction equation of Fourier only in the through-thickness direction :

$$\sum_{i=1}^3 \frac{\partial q_i}{\partial x_i} = -K_z \frac{\partial^2 T}{\partial z^2} \tag{7}$$

where z is the co-ordinate in the through-tickness direction and K_z is the corresponding heat conduction coefficient, equation (1) may be modified into the following form :

$$\frac{\partial \theta}{\partial t} - \gamma \frac{\partial^2 \theta}{\partial z^2} = S \quad (8)$$

Equation (8) is a classical one-dimensional diffusion equation where $\gamma = \frac{K_z}{\rho c \sigma}$ is the coefficient of

$$\text{thermal diffusivity and } S = - \frac{1}{\rho c \sigma} [\alpha_{11} \dot{\sigma}_{11} + \alpha_{22} \dot{\sigma}_{22}] \quad (9)$$

represents the internal heat source.

The recommended solution method for this type of problem is a Crank-Nicolson finite difference scheme. In contrast to the explicit finite difference scheme the implicit Crank-Nicolson scheme is unconditionally stable; the size of Δt is restricted only by the demands of accuracy, and not by stability. Convergence occurs always to this correct equilibrium solution.

To obtain a solution, initial and boundary conditions are required. At $t = 0$, we assume that the body is at thermal equilibrium with the surrounding, so that $\theta(x=x_i, t=0) = 0$.

As we studied only laminates which have symmetry about their midplanes, we assume adiabatic boundary conditions on the midplane. On the free surface, we assume convective boundary conditions.

4. NUMERICAL AND EXPERIMENTAL RESULTS.

The code developed to run on a PC, discretises each ply by 20 nodes and uses a time-step of $0.01 \pi/\omega$ s (period / 200) for all frequencies studied. At every time step the complete temperature field was solved, but only the surface temperature was monitored as this corresponded to the value which would be detected by the SPATE's infra-red sensor. Following the convention of DUNN et al. [11] all amplitude data were normalised by the SPATE data at 20Hz.

The data presented concerns quasi-isotropic CFRP-specimens with different stacking sequences. It is clearly shown how difficult the interpretation of SPATE data, to reflect the stresses in fibre reinforced composite, is.

As the heat sources in the different layers are quite different, indeed $S = 1.0 a \omega \cos \omega t$ for the 0° -layer, $S = 4.6 a \omega \cos \omega t$ for the 90° ply and $S = 2.8 a \omega \cos \omega t$ for the angle-ply, the stacking sequence becomes extremely important. The fact whether the surface ply is a 0° -ply or the 90° -ply will change the surface temperature response dramatically.

It is seen from figure 1 that for the $[(0^\circ, +45^\circ, 90^\circ, -45^\circ)_2]_S$ specimen the SPATE response at 1 Hz is 2.5 times higher compared to the response at 20 Hz.

On the other hand for the $[(90^\circ, +45^\circ, 0^\circ, -45^\circ)_2]_S$ specimen the SPATE data at 1 Hz is reduced to 65% of the response at 20 Hz. When we make the 45° -ply the surface layer the variation of the surface temperature response depending on the frequency is largely reduced, indeed the maximum response at 5 Hz is less than 20% above the response at 20 Hz.

Fig. 1. Normalised Amplitude of θ_s for different stackings of quasi-isotropic laminates.

In general, we may conclude that the model presented describes very well the thermoelastic behaviour of fibre reinforced composite systems. The agreement between the numerical prediction and the experimental measurement is quite satisfactory.

5. CONCLUSIONS

It is shown that a model including the thermal conduction is quite accurate. The three-dimensional model indicated that the convective heat losses to the surrounding may be neglected certainly when the loading frequency is higher than 5 Hz. For the same loading conditions, it is found that the thermal conduction in the in-plane directions is very low and the stress-induced thermal effects are quite local. The one-dimensional model demonstrated very good agreement with the experimental measurements, and indicated the large importance of the thermal conduction in the through-thickness direction on the surface temperature changes for some composite systems. It is concluded that thinking of SPATE as a "surface" stress analysis device is completely untrue in some cases.